

Novel 2,6-diformyl-4-methyl phenol based chemosensor for Zn^{II} ion by ratiometric displacement of Cd^{II} ion and its application for cell imaging on human melanoma cancer cells

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Abstract : A new chelating ligand [4-methyl-2,6-bis-(pyridin-2-yl-hydrazonomethyl)-phenol] (1) was prepared by the condensation of 2-hydrazinylpyridine with 2,6-diformyl-*p*-cresol. Compound 1 exhibits weak fluorescence due to intramolecular photoinduced electron transfer (PET). The sensor (1) demonstrates Zn²⁺-specific emission enhancement due to “PET off” process through a 1 : 1 binding mode with the metal ion. The fluorescence quantum yield of the chemosensor 1 is only 0.020, and it increases more than 14-fold (0.280) in the presence of one equivalent of the zinc ion. Interestingly, the introduction of other metal ions causes the fluorescence intensity to remain either unchanged or weakened except for Cd²⁺. Ratiometric displacement of Cd²⁺ ion from the complex by Zn²⁺ ion supports the formation of more stable sensor-Zn²⁺ complex over the sensor-Cd²⁺ complex. The experimental findings have been correlated with theoretical results using B3LYP functional and 6-31G(d,p), LANL2DZ basis set for Cd²⁺ (2) and Zn²⁺ (3) complex, respectively, by Density Functional Theory (DFT) method. Moreover, the ability of probe 1 to sense Zn²⁺ within human melanoma cancer cells has been explored, and the Zn²⁺-probing process in living cells was reversible. [Mn₂(PHMP)₂](ClO₄)₂ (4) and [Ni₂(PHMP)(H₂O)₅](NO₃)₃ (5) have been also synthesized and characterized crystallographically and spectroscopically to understand the ligating behavior of the ligand PHMP.

Keywords : Chemosensor, Zn^{II} ion, Cd^{II} ion, photoinduced electron transfer, density functional theory, human melanoma cancer cells.

Introduction

Zinc ion is an essential metal in the human body¹ and plays an important role in various fundamental biological processes, such as gene transcription, regulation of metalloenzymes^{2,3}. Disruption of Zn^{II} homeostasis has been associated with several pathologies, including is-

chemia⁴, Alzheimer's disease^{5,6} and prostate cancer^{7,8}. Ever increasing concerns for ecological issues such as the potential toxicity of zinc pollutants drive the need for more effective detection methods, selective and versatile sensors. A literature survey indicates that many fluorescent probes have been designed which operate on Photo-

induced Electron Transfer, Internal Charge Transfer (ICT) or Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer mechanisms⁹⁻¹². Although significant progress has been made in relation to the detection of Zn^{2+} ion, still there is a demand for a fluororeceptor of new architecture with improved fluorescent properties. Being group 12 elements of the periodic table Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} show cross-reactivity and record similar spectral changes while coordinated with fluorescent sensors. To date, the common probes for Zn^{2+} are derivatives of Zinquin¹³, 8-aminoquinoline¹⁴, the Zinpyr family¹⁵, Zinbo-5¹⁶, coumarin¹⁷ and the TQEN¹⁸ family. However, the development of fluorescent chemosensors that can selectively recognize one of the multiple analytes, especially species with similar chemical properties such as Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+} etc. has been an active topic of current research because of operational simplicity and high sensitivity¹⁹. The fluorescent detection and imaging of target biological molecules of interest in living systems have become also an active research area.

In this paper, we have reported a novel 4-methyl-2,6-bis-(pyridin-2-yl-hydrazone-methyl)-phenol (**1**) as a 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol-based highly selective and sensitive fluorescent probe for sensing Zn^{2+} in a (HEPES) buffer [pH = 7.2] at 25 °C by ratiometric displacement of Cd^{II} ion (Scheme 1). The chemosensor (**1**) has been characterised by ESI-MS (Fig. 1). The most interesting

Scheme 1. Showing (a) Cd^{2+} binds with **1**, (b) Zn^{2+} replaces Cd^{2+} and (c) EDTA replaces Zn^{2+} .

Fig. 1. ESI-MS of the chemosensor **1**.

feature is that **1** can be successfully applied for sensing Zn^{2+} in DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), and in human melanoma cancer cells, claiming to be a promising agent in clarifying the roles of Zn^{2+} in biological processes.

Experimental

Materials and physical methods :

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents were purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification. Solvents were dried by standard methods. 2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol²⁰ and 2-hydrazinyl pyridine²¹ were prepared by literature methods. All reagents and chemicals were purchased from Sigma and used without further purification. Solvents used for spectroscopic studies were purified and dried by standard procedures before use. Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were determined with a Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer 2400. The UV-Vis spectra of all samples were studied with Hewlett-Packard UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Model 8453). IR spectra (KBr pellet, 400–4000 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 883 infrared spectrophotometer. Fluorescence studies were carried out with Horiba Jobin Yvon Fluoromax 3 instrument at excited wavelength 280 nm for ligand and 350 nm for complex **2** and **3**. Fluorescence lifetimes were measured by the method of Time Correlated Single-Photon counting (TCSPC) using a HORIBA Jobin Yvon Fluorocube-01-NL fluorescence lifetime spectrometer. The sample was excited using a nanosecond laser diode at 340 nm and the signals were collected at the magic angle of 54.7° to eliminate any considerable contribution from fluorescence anisotropy

decay²². The typical time resolution of our experimental set-up is ~ 800 ps. The decays were deconvoluted using DAS-6 decay analysis software. The acceptability of the fits was judged by χ^2 criteria and visual inspection of the residuals of the fitted function to the data. Mean (average) fluorescence lifetimes were calculated using the following equation²³ :

$$\tau_{av} = \frac{\sum \alpha_i \tau_i^2}{\sum \alpha_i \tau_i}$$

in which α_i is the pre-exponential factor corresponding to the i -th decay time constant, τ_i .

Reagents for cell study :

A375, a human melanocarcinoma cell line, was procured from National Center for Cell Science, Pune, India, and used throughout the study. Cells were cultured in DMEM (Gibco BRL) supplemented with 10% FBS (Gibco BRL), and 1% antibiotic mixture containing PSN (Gibco BRL) at 37 °C in a humidified incubator with 5% CO₂ and cells were grown to 80–90% confluence, harvested with 0.025% trypsin (Gibco BRL) and 0.52 mM EDTA (Gibco BRL) in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), plated at the desired cell concentration and allowed to reequilibrate for 24 h before any treatment. All experiments were conducted in DMEM containing 10% FBS and 1% PSN antibiotic.

Computational method :

Full geometry optimizations of the complexes **2** and **3** were carried out using the density functional theory method at the B3LYP level²⁴ with Gaussian 03 program package²⁵. The 6-31G(d) basis set was employed for all the elements except Zn and Cd atoms. For Zn and Cd, we used the lanL2DZ basis set, including Los Alamos Effective Core Potentials²⁶. The vibrational frequency calculations were performed to ensure that the optimized geometries represent the local minima of potential energy surface and there are only positive eigenvalues. The lowest 40 singlet-singlet vertical electronic excitations based on B3LYP optimized geometries were computed for the time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT) formalism²⁷ in methanol using conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)²⁸. GaussSum²⁹ was used to calculate the fractional contributions of various groups to each molecular orbital.

Synthesis of the chemosensor (PHMP) (1) :

2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol was synthesized starting from *p*-cresol and following a published procedure¹⁹. A methanolic solution (20 ml) of 2-hydrazino pyridine (0.218 g, 2 mmol) was added dropwise to the methanolic solution (15 ml) of 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol (0.164 g, 1 mmol) with constant stirring (Scheme 2). The stirring was continued for 30 min and the mixture was re-

Scheme 2. Preparation of the chemosensor **1**.

fluxed for 5 h under water bath temperature and cooled to room temperature. Excess methanol was removed in a rotary evaporator to have a yellow microcrystalline solid. The solid was filtered off, washed thoroughly with cold methanol and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂.

Yield : (0.305 g, 80%), m.p. 245 °C (decomp.), MS (m/z) 346 (M⁺, 100%); IR (cm⁻¹) : ν_{NH} 3325; $\nu_{CO/CN}$ 1661(s), 1597(s); ν_{N-N} 1051(s); ν_{py} 1023(s). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈N₆O : C, 65.89; H, 5.20; N, 24.27. Found : C, 65.72; H, 5.26; N, 24.21%.

Syntheses of [Cd₂(PHMP)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2) and [Zn₂(PHMP)₂](ClO₄)₂ (3) :

The ligand PHMP (3.46 g, 10 mmol) was added to a hot solution of Cd(ClO₄)₂.6H₂O (4.19 g, 10 mmol) in CH₃OH-CH₃CN (30 mL) [1 : 1 (v/v)]. The suspension was stirred for 2 h with constant stirring until complete dissolution of the ligand occurred. The resulting yellow solution was filtered to remove any undissolved ligand and left at room temperature. Yellow crystals suitable for

X-ray diffraction were isolated after standing for several days (yield 80%). IR (cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{NH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ 3401, 3385; $\nu_{\text{CO}/\text{CN}}$ 1625(s), 1539(s); $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ 1084(s); ν_{py} 1019(s); UV-Vis (λ_{max}): 233, 322, 371 nm. Anal. Calcd. for $[\text{Cd}_2(\text{PHMP})_2(\mu_2\text{-O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**): C, 40.86; H, 3.22; N, 30.11. Found: C, 40.87; H, 3.24; N, 30.09%.

Complex **3** was prepared similarly using $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ instead of $\text{Cd}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (yield 75%). IR (cm^{-1}): $\nu_{\text{NH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ 3401, 3385; $\nu_{\text{CO}/\text{CN}}$ 1623(s), 1537(s); $\nu_{\text{N-N}}$ 1082(s); ν_{py} 1019(s); UV-Vis (λ_{max}): 237, 321, 372 nm. Anal. Calcd. for $[\text{Zn}_2(\text{PHMP})_2(\mu_2\text{-O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**1**): C, 44.62; H, 3.52; N, 32.87. Found: C, 44.64; H, 3.50; N, 32.84%.

Preparation of $[\text{Mn}_2(\text{PHMP})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (**4**):

To a hot ($\sim 60^\circ\text{C}$) methanol-acetonitrile solution (1 : 1) of the ligand PHMP (3.46 g, 10 mmol) a solution of $\text{Mn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3.71 g, 10 mmol) in the same solvent was added with stirring condition. Two drops of triethyl amine in methanol solution was added to it. The resulting red colored solution was stirred for an additional 2 h. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was kept for slow evaporation. After three days, red colored single crystals, suitable for X-ray diffraction were separated (yield 70.1%). Anal. Calcd. for : C, 45.66; H, 3.43; N, 16.82. Found : C, 45.67; H, 3.45; N, 16.83%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1622, 1597, 1564, 1532, 1297.

Preparation of $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{PHMP})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_5](\text{NO}_3)_3$ (**5**):

A methanolic solution (5 ml) of $\text{Ni}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (3.65 g, 10 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of PHMP (3.46 g, 10 mmol) in the same solvent (15 ml) with constant stirring. The resulting brown colored solution was further stirred for *ca.* 0.5 h. A yellowish brown colour compound was precipitated out. On addition of acetonitrile (10 ml) the precipitated compound dissolved and the solution became deep red. The solution was stirred for 1 h. Then the solution was filtered and the filtrate was kept for slow evaporation. After few days X-ray quality crystals of **2** were collected (yield 65.5%). Anal. Calcd. for : C, 30.89; H, 3.68; N, 17.06. Found : C, 30.87; H, 3.69; N, 17.08%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1614, 1529, 1489, 1434, 1297.

X-Ray data collection and structure determination of **2**, **4** and **5**:

The complex **2**, **4** and **5** was mounted on a Cryoloop

with Paratone-N oil and data was collected at 100 K with a Bruker APEX CCD system using Mo K alpha radiation. The crystallographic and structural refinement of **2**, **4** and **5** are listed in Table 1. Data corrected for absorption with SADABS and structure solved by direct methods³⁰. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically by Fourier full matrix least squares on F^2 . Hydrogen atoms on N2 and N5 were found from a Fourier difference map and were allowed to refine while all other hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions with appropriate riding models.

Fluorimetric analysis :

Fluorescence quantum yields (ϕ) were estimated by integrating the area under the fluorescence curves with the equation,

$$\Phi_{\text{sample}} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{standard}} \times A_{\text{sample}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{sample}} \times A_{\text{standard}}} \times \Phi_{\text{standard}}$$

where A is the area under the fluorescence spectral curve and OD is the optical density of the compound at the excitation wavelength. The standard used for the measurement of the fluorescence quantum yield was anthracene ($\phi = 0.32$ in ethanol).

Imaging system :

The imaging system was composed of a fluorescence microscope (Model : LEICA DMLS) with an objective lens of 20X magnification.

Cell culture :

Cells were rinsed with PBS and incubated with DMEM containing chemosensor **1** making the final concentration up to 20 μM in DMEM [the stock solution (1 mM) was prepared by dissolving chemosensor **1** to the mixed solvent (DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v))] for 10 min at 37 $^\circ\text{C}$. After incubation, bright field and fluorescence images of A375 cells were taken by a fluorescence microscope (Model : LEICA DMLS) with an objective lens of 20X magnification as well as fluorescence images of A375 cells (pre-incubated with 20 μM **1**) were taken with the addition of different concentrations (10–50 μM) of zinc nitrate salt at 10 min interval and consequently fluorescence images were taken after further addition of either EDTA (100 μM) or TPEN (100 μM).

Cell cytotoxicity assay :

In order to test the cytotoxicity of the chemosensor **1**,

Table 1. Crystallographic data of **2**, **4** and **5**

Compound	2	4	5
Empirical formula	C ₃₈ H ₃₄ Cd ₂ Cl ₂ N ₁₂ O ₁₀	C ₃₈ H ₃₂ Cl ₂ Mn ₂ N ₁₂ O ₁₀	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₉ Ni ₂ O ₁₅
Formula weight	1114.47	997.54	738.88
Temperature (K)	100(2)	296(2)	150(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073	0.71073	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Orthorhombic
Space group	C2/c	P2/c	Pbca
Unit cell dimensions			
<i>a</i> (Å)	23.0762(15)	11.063(6)	21.612(6)
<i>b</i> (Å)	12.6124(6)	11.836(6)	9.286(3)
<i>c</i> (Å)	17.5274(13)	18.028(9)	29.788(9)
α (°)	90.00	90.00	90.00
β (°)	116.6010(10)	105.217(6)	90.00
γ (°)	90.00	90.00	90.00
Volume (Å ³)	4561.3(5)	2278(2)	5978(3)
<i>z</i>	4	2	8
Density _{cal} (Mg m ⁻³)	1.623	1.454	1.642
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	1.117	0.739	1.343
F(000)	2224	1016	3040
θ Range (°) for data collection	1.89 to 27.98	1.7 to 20.6	1.37 to 25.10
Index ranges	-30 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 29 -16 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 16 -23 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 22	-10 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 10 -11 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11 -17 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17	-25 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 25 -11 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11 -35 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 35
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.036	1.075	1.068
Completeness to theta			
Independent reflections [R _{int}]	5299 [0.036]	2303 [0.046]	5210 [0.098]
Refinement method	Full-matrix least squares on F ²	Full-matrix least squares on F ²	Full-matrix least squares on F ²
Data/restraints/parameters	5299/0/299	2303/0/295	5210/0/454
Reflections collected	29240	9919	31124
Final R indices [I > 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0627, wR ₂ = 0.0581	R ₁ = 0.2183, wR ₂ = 0.2081	R ₁ = 0.2237, wR ₂ = 0.2030
R indices (all data)	R ₁ = 0.0341, wR ₂ = 0.0237	R ₁ = 0.0754, wR ₂ = 0.0683	R ₁ = 0.1237, wR ₂ = 0.0758
Largest difference peak and hole (eÅ ⁻³)	-0.42 and 0.56	-0.47 and 1.46	-0.59 and 1.38

3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,6-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) assay was performed by the procedure described earlier³¹. After treatment with chemosensor **1** (1, 10, 20, 50 and 100 μM) for 4 h, 10 μL of a MTT solution (10 mg/ml PBS) was added in each well of a 96-well culture plate and incubated continuously at 37 °C for 3 h. All media were removed from wells and 100 μL of acidic isopropyl alcohol was added into each well. The intracellular formazan crystals (blue-violet) formed were solubilized with 0.04 N acidic isopropyl alcohol and absorbance of the solution was measured at 595 nm wave-

length with a microplate reader (Model : THERMO MULTI SCAN EX). The cell viability was expressed as the optical density ratio of the treatment to control. Values are mean ± standard deviation of three independent experiments. The cell cytotoxicity was calculated as % cell cytotoxicity = 100% - % cell viability.

Results and discussion

Complexes **2**, **3**, **4** and **5** were prepared from 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol. **2** and **3** were synthesized in a very facile and identical way. **2**, **4** and **5** was character-

ized by X-ray crystallographic analyses, elemental analyses, IR, UV-Vis spectra.

Structural description of [Cd₂(PHMP)₂](ClO₄)₂ (2) :

View of the cationic motif in **2** is displayed in Fig. 2; selected bond lengths and angles are listed in Table 2. The complex **2** crystallises in space group C2/c and its unit cell comprises of four molecules. The structure is built up of dinuclear Cd₂(L)₂²⁺ entities in which two cadmium centres are connected through double alkoxo bridges.

Fig. 2. Structural representation and atom numbering scheme of the cationic complex **2**.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) data for **2**, **4** and **5**

Selected bonds	Value (Å)	Selected angles	(°)
Complex 2			
Cd1-O1	2.2440(13)	O1-Cd1-N1	141.53(7)
Cd1-N1	2.2946(19)	O1-Cd1-N3	74.75(6)
Cd1-N3	2.339(2)	O1-Cd1-O1_a	73.94(5)
Cd1-O1_a	2.2440(13)	O1-Cd1-N1_a	107.57(6)
Cd1-N1_a	2.2946(19)	O1-Cd1-N3_a	117.86(6)
Cd1-N3_a	2.339(2)	N1-Cd1-N3	70.93(6)
Cd2-O1	2.2449(13)	O1_a-Cd1-N1	107.57(6)
Cd2-N4	2.301(2)	N1-Cd1-N1_a	94.49(7)
Cd2-N6	2.3627(18)	N1-Cd1-N3_a	98.82(6)
Cd2-O1_a	2.2449(13)	O1_a-Cd1-N3	117.86(6)
Cd2-N4_a	2.301(2)	N1_a-Cd1-N3	98.82(6)
Cd2-N6_a	2.3627(18)	N3-Cd1-N3_a	165.31(6)
		O1_a-Cd1-N1_a	141.53(7)
		O1_a-Cd1-N3_a	74.75(6)

Table-2 (contd.)

N1_a-Cd1-N3_a	70.93(6)	O1-Mn1-N1	143.2(2)
O1-Cd2-N4	103.06(6)	O1-Mn1-N2	120.2(2)
O1-Cd2-N6	125.23(6)	O1-Mn1-O1_a	73.89(18)
O1-Cd2-O1_a	73.90(5)	O1-Mn1-N1_a	105.8(2)
O1-Cd2-N4_a	132.74(7)	O1-Mn1-N2_a	76.60(19)
O1-Cd2-N6_a	74.04(6)	N1-Mn1-N2	94.6(2)
N4-Cd2-N6	70.21(6)	O1_a-Mn1-N1	105.8(2)
O1_a-Cd2-N4	132.74(7)	N1-Mn1-N1_a	95.8(2)
N4-Cd2-N4_a	111.06(7)	N1-Mn1-N2_a	72.1(2)
N4-Cd2-N6_a	97.17(7)	O1_a-Mn1-N2	76.60(19)
O1_a-Cd2-N6	74.04(6)	N1_a-Mn1-N2	72.1(2)
N4_a-Cd2-N6	97.17(7)	N2-Mn1-N2_a	160.5(2)
N6-Cd2-N6_a	158.22(6)	O1_a-Mn1-N1_a	143.2(2)
O1_a-Cd2-N4_a	103.06(6)	O1_a-Mn1-N2_a	120.2(2)
O1_a-Cd2-N6_a	125.23(6)	N1_a-Mn1-N2_a	94.6(2)
N4_a-Cd2-N6_a	70.21(6)	O1-Mn2-N4	76.6(2)
Complex 4			
Mn1-O1	2.101(4)	O1-Mn2-N6	141.0(2)
Mn1-N1	2.203(6)	O1-Mn2-O1_a	73.41(18)
Mn1-N2	2.278(6)	O1-Mn2-N4_a	123.1(2)
Mn1-O1_a	2.101(4)	O1-Mn2-N6_a	105.5(2)
Mn1-N1_a	2.203(6)	N4-Mn2-N6	71.9(2)
Mn1-N2_a	2.278(6)	O1_a-Mn2-N4	123.1(2)
Mn2-O1	2.112(4)	N4-Mn2-N4_a	157.4(2)
Mn2-N4	2.259(5)	N4-Mn2-N6_a	93.2(2)
Mn2-N6	2.210(7)	O1_a-Mn2-N6	105.5(2)
Mn2-O1_a	2.112(4)	N4_a-Mn2-N6	93.2(2)
Mn2-N4_a	2.259(5)	N6-Mn2-N6_a	98.7(3)
Mn2-N6_a	2.210(7)	O1_a-Mn2-N4_a	76.6(2)
		O1_a-Mn2-N6_a	141.0(2)

Table-2 (contd.)

		N4_a-Mn2-N6_a	71.9(2)
		Mn1-O1-Mn2	106.4(2)
		Mn1-N2-N3	114.2(4)
		Mn2-N4-N5	114.2(4)
Complex 5			
Ni1-O1	2.011(7)	O1-Ni1-O2	81.2(2)
Ni1-O2	2.116(7)	O1-Ni1-O4	94.2(2)
Ni1-O4	2.059(6)	O1-Ni1-O6	89.6(3)
Ni1-O6	2.088(7)	O1-Ni1-N1	171.3(3)
Ni1-N1	2.049(9)	O1-Ni1-N3	90.4(2)
Ni1-N3	1.970(7)	O2-Ni1-O4	87.7(2)
Ni2-O1	2.004(6)	O2-Ni1-O6	87.6(3)
Ni2-O2	2.115(7)	O2-Ni1-N1	107.5(3)
Ni2-O3	2.088(6)	O2-Ni1-N3	171.6(3)
Ni2-O5	2.103(8)	O4-Ni1-O6	173.5(3)
Ni2-N4	1.965(7)	O4-Ni1-N1	86.1(3)
Ni2-N6	2.028(7)	O4-Ni1-N3	92.9(3)
		O6-Ni1-N1	91.1(3)
		O6-Ni1-N3	92.5(3)
		N1-Ni1-N3	80.9(3)
		O1-Ni2-O2	81.4(3)
		O1-Ni2-O3	87.5(2)
		O1-Ni2-O5	92.5(3)
		O1-Ni2-N4	91.4(3)
		O1-Ni2-N6	171.9(3)
		O2-Ni2-O3	87.9(3)
		O2-Ni2-O5	89.3(3)
		O2-Ni2-N4	172.7(3)
		O2-Ni2-N6	106.0(3)
		O3-Ni2-O5	177.2(3)
		O3-Ni2-N4	93.2(3)
		O3-Ni2-N6	89.4(3)
		O5-Ni2-N4	89.7(3)
		O5-Ni2-N6	91.0(3)
		Ni1-O1-Ni2	101.9(3)
		Ni1-O2-Ni2	94.9(3)

Structural description of [Mn₂(PHMP)₂](ClO₄)₂ (4) :

The molecular structure of dinuclear manganese(II) complex with its atom numbering scheme is illustrated in Fig. 3. Selected bond lengths and bond angles are presented in Table 2. Complex 4 crystallizes in the P_{21/c} space group and the unit cell of the complex comprises of two molecules. In the structure of the complex 1 a pair of monoanionic ligands bridge a pair of Mn^{II} centers using the alkoxide ions. The manganese centers exhibit a dis-

Fig. 3. Structural representation and atom numbering scheme of the cationic complex 1.

torted six coordinated octahedral geometry, where two pyridine nitrogen (N6/N6_a for Mn1 and N1/N1_a for Mn2) and two μ_2 bridging phenoxy oxygen atom (O1, O2 for both Mn1 and Mn2) constitute the basal plane. The apical positions are occupied by two imino nitrogens (N4 and N4_a for Mn1 and N2 and N2_a for Mn2; N2-Mn1-N2_a = 160.5(2) $^\circ$ and N4-Mn2-N4_a = 157.4(2) $^\circ$). The separation between two manganese centers is 3.372 \AA . The charge of the complex is neutralized by two ionic perchlorates. The mean plane constituted by two cresol ring including its *para* phenoxo group (mean planes are C₆C₇C₅C₄C₂O₁ and C₄C₅C₆O₁C₇C₂C₃) make an angle 84.70 $^\circ$ which tells that the two ligand molecules are more or less orthogonal in nature to minimize the steric repulsion. The manganese-nitrogen bond lengths can vary from 2.203 \AA to 2.278 \AA . The manganese-oxygen bond distances are 2.101 \AA and 2.112 \AA . The angle between the planes constituted by the pyridine ring (N₁C₁₃C₁₂C₁₁C₁₀C₉ and N₁C₉C₁₀C₁₁C₁₂C₁₃) is 79.47 $^\circ$. The departure from the ideal *cis* angle 90 $^\circ$ and ideal *trans* angle 180 $^\circ$ is probably due to the steric requirements.

Structural description of [Ni₂(PHMP)(H₂O)₅](NO₃)₃ (5) :

The molecular structure of dinuclear μ -oxo bridged Ni^{II} complex with the atom numbering scheme is illustrated in Fig. 4. Complex 5 crystallizes in the P_{bca} space group and the unit cell contains 8 molecules. Relevant bond lengths and angle are supplied in Table 2. Each Ni center in 2 is surrounded octahedrally by two nitrogen (pyridine nitrogen N1, azomethine nitrogen N3) and four oxygen atoms among which one μ -oxo oxygen (O1) and remaining three oxygens from coordinated water mole-

Fig. 4. Structural representation and atom numbering scheme of the cationic complex **2**.

cules (O2, O4, O6 for Ni1 and O2, O3, O5 for Ni2). Around Ni1, the equatorial square plane is constituted by pyrimidine nitrogen N1, azomethine nitrogen N3 and one μ -oxo oxygen O1 and one coordinated water oxygen O2 ($\text{N3Ni1N1} = 80.9(3)^\circ$, $\text{N1Ni1O2} = 107.5(3)^\circ$, $\text{O2Ni1O1} = 81.2(2)^\circ$ and $\text{O1Ni1N3} = 90.4(2)^\circ$) and the axial positions are occupied by two coordinated water molecule (O4 and O6, $\angle \text{O4Ni1O6} = 173.5(3)^\circ$). Similarly for Ni2, the equatorial positions are coordinated by one pyridine nitrogen (N6), one azomethine nitrogen N4 and μ_2 -oxo oxygen (O1) and one bridging water oxygen (O2) ($\text{O1Ni2N4} = 91.4(3)^\circ$, $\text{O1Ni2O2} = 81.4(3)^\circ$ and $\text{O2Ni2N6} = 106(3)^\circ$) and the axial positions are satisfied by two coordinating water molecule (O3 and O5; $\text{O3NiO5} = 177.2(3)^\circ$). The Ni1 is shifted from the plane constituted by N1O2O1N3 by 0.004 Å towards O4, and the same for Ni2 (equatorial plane is N4O1O2N6) is 0.020 Å towards O3. Among the *cis* angles around each Ni center it has been observed that there is a large departure from the ideal 90° for N1Ni1O2 (around Ni1) and O2Ni2N6 (around Ni2) which may be ascribed due to the absence of any spacer between N1 and O2 (for Ni1) and O2 and N6 (for Ni2). The Ni-O bond distances vary from 2.004 Å to 2.116 Å which are somewhat comparable to the data reported in other complexes. The Ni-Ni distance in **2** is 3.117 Å. In the equatorial plane N1-O1 and N3-O2 are more or less in a *trans* orientation ($\text{O1Ni1N1} = 171.3(3)^\circ$ and $\text{O2Ni1N3} = 171.3(3)^\circ$) around Ni1 and N6-O1 and N4-O2 are also in a *trans* orientation ($\text{N4Ni2O2} = 172.7(3)^\circ$ and $\text{O1Ni2N6} = 171.9(3)^\circ$) around the Ni2 atom.

The charge of the complex is balanced by the presence of a monoanionic ligand molecule three non-coordi-

nated nitrate anions. It is generally observed that the water molecules can behave as a monodentate ligand by donating one of its lone pair of electrons to the metal ion but here one water molecule surprisingly behave as a bridging ligand by involvement of both lone pairs of electrons to two different Ni atoms. The noncoordinated nitrate ion forms a strong H-bonding interaction with the hydrogen of the coordinated water molecules and further stabilizes the structure of **2**.

Within the subunits, the six-coordinate Cd ions are bridged by the deprotonated phenolic oxygen of the ligand at a distance of 3.587 Å. Further donor atoms are the imine and pyridine nitrogens of the ligand side arms. The Cd1-O1-Cd2 angle of $106.08(6)^\circ$ compares well with the values reported for mono(μ -oxo) dicadmium complexes. There are two perchlorate anions present in each dimeric unit. The coordination of Cd is satisfied by N_4O_2 chromophore. The equatorial plane consists of N1-N3-N3_a-O1 and N4-N6-N6_a-O1_a for Cd1 and Cd2 respectively. The axial positions are occupied by the N1_a and O1_a for Cd1 and N4_a and O1_a for Cd2. The equatorial and the axial bond distances are fall in the ranges 2.2440–2.339 and 2.2440–2.301 for both the Cd centres.

Absorbance studies :

Fig. 5 depicts spectrophotometric changes upon titrating a fixed concentration of **1** (40 μM) with incremental additions of $\text{Zn}(\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (100 μM) in MeOH using HEPES buffer [50 μM , DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2].

Fig. 5. UV-Vis spectral changes of **1** (40 μM) upon the addition of Zn^{2+} in a HEPES buffer [50 μM , DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$, $[\text{Zn}^{2+}] = 5\text{--}100 \mu\text{M}$.

The absorption spectrum of **1** in aqueous methanol (1×10^{-6} M) displayed a broad ILCT absorption band centered at 237 nm, 321 nm and 372 nm (Fig. 2). However, addition of Zn²⁺ induced dramatic modification both in the maximas and shape of the said bands of **1**. The band maxima at 237 nm gradually shifted to 246 nm and the band at 321 nm gradually decreased and three new bands appeared at 295 nm, 326 nm and 343 nm. The band at 372 nm was diminished and a new sharp peak arisen at 404 nm and finally the colourless solution turned yellow. This absorption peaks were expected to correspond to coordination of **1** with Zn²⁺. These phenomena illustrated the transformation from free **1** to the Zn²⁺-coordinated species (**3**). UV-Visible spectral response of **1** (1×10^{-6} M) upon introducing perchlorates of biologically significant ions such as Li⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Ag⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Pb²⁺ (100 μ M) showed a marginal shift of the ILCT band of **1** with a slight decrease in band intensity.

The change in color of chemosensor **1** (10 μ M) upon addition of Zn²⁺ ions (10 μ M) was clearly visible under visible light through naked-eye whereas in presence other metal ions the metal-ligand solution were colorless. A bright blue fluorescence was observed only for **1**+Zn²⁺ solution and to a little bit extent for **1**+Cd²⁺ under UV-light. This is an interesting feature by which we can detect Zn²⁺ without any other instrumental technique.

Fluorescence properties and binding behavior :

Fig. 6 shows the various metal dependent emission intensity at 476 nm for different metal ions in methanol

Fig. 6. Emission spectra of **1** (40 μ M) in the presence of Zn²⁺, Li⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mn²⁺, Fe³⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ag⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺ and Pb²⁺ (100 μ M each metal ions) in a HEPES buffer [50 μ M, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 °C (λ_{exc} = 350 nm).

using HEPES buffer [50 μ M, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 °C (λ_{exc} = 350 nm). Evidently, the changes in the emission spectral profile of **1** were significantly more pronounced in presence of Zn²⁺ (Φ = 0.280) compared to those other metal ions. It is noteworthy to mention here that unlike many other Zn²⁺ sensors reported so far where Cd²⁺, a stereoelectronic isostere of Zn²⁺ was found to interfere with the sensing but **1** showed negligible fluorescent enhancement to the emission centred at 476 nm in the presence of Cd²⁺ (Φ = 0.130), thereby making it advantageous to distinguish between these two ions.

The fluorescence intensity of **1** (40 μ M) significantly increased when various concentrations of Zn²⁺ (5–100 μ M) were added (Fig. 7), and the fluorescence quantum yield (0.280) increased more than 14-fold. This enhance-

Fig. 7. Emission spectra of **1** (40 μ M) in the presence of various concentrations of Zn²⁺ in a HEPES buffer [50 μ M, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 °C (λ_{exc} = 350 nm).

ment is attributed to the introduction of Zn²⁺ along with the strong complexation occurring with **1**, as is evident from the large binding constant value, 3.1×10^7 mol⁻¹ L³¹. Upon complexation, the lone pair of electrons on the N atom of the chemosensor **1** is no longer available for PET, leading to fluorescence enhancement. In addition, the enhancement of the fluorescence intensity was due to the formation of a **1**-Zn²⁺ complex, which resulted in the selective CHEF effect. Interestingly, the introduction of other metal ions causes the fluorescence intensity to be either unchanged or weakened. A metal ion selectivity study (Fig. 8) was then performed for **1** to understand

Fig. 8. Relative emission intensity change profile of the chemosensor **1** (1.0 μM) in the presence of various metal ions at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 350 \text{ nm}$) in a HEPES buffer (50 μM , DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2).

this phenomenon under identical experimental conditions. The fluorescence intensity of **1** (1 μM) was unaffected upon the addition of Li^+ , Na^+ , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ag^+ , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Pb^{2+} (100 μM). Detailed investigations were carried out to understand the coordinating behavior of **1** with Zn^{2+} ions. The stoichiometry of the coordinating species was examined by the method of continuous variation (Job's plot) and found to be 1 : 1 with respect to **1** to Zn^{2+} (Fig. 9). Based on this spectral evidence, mass spectral and CHN analysis, the **1**+ Zn^{2+} complex was proposed to have the

Fig. 9. Job's plot analysis in HEPES buffer (50 μM , DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2) shows that the maximum intensity was obtained at $X = 0.50$ indicates the probable 1 : 1 binding of **1** : Zn^{2+} (excitation wavelength : 350 nm).

molecular structure as shown in Fig. 10. The peak at 410.9852 seems to correspond to a peak with a +2 charge based on some of the peaks separation (0.5 mass unit : 411.9780, 412.4804, 412.9830). As pH dependence of fluorescence is generally undesirable in biological applications, the effect of pH on fluorescence was also studied in methanol. It was found that the fluorescence intensity of **1** at 479 nm remained unaffected between pH 5.5 and 9 which makes it suitable for application in physiological conditions (Fig. 11).

These results indicate that **1** can be used as a selective fluorescent probe to recognize and distinguish Zn^{2+} in the presence of various interfering and biologically relevant metal ions. We also carried out a reversibility experiment which proved that Zn^{2+} binding to **1** is reversible. A key requirement for an ideal chemosensor function is that guest binding must occur reversibly. As shown in Fig. 12, after the addition of EDTA (100 μM), the emission intensity of **1**+ Zn^{2+} complex was almost completely quenched. The reaction of this Zn^{2+} complex solution with the chelating ligand EDTA ended up with the formation of the original ligand (quantum yield = 0.020). Obviously this gives a tacit support towards the reversible binding of the ligand with formation of the Zn^{2+} .

Ratiometric displacement of Cd^{2+} by Zn^{2+} :

The ratiometric displacement of Cd^{2+} ion from L- Cd^{2+} complex by Zn^{2+} ion was studied from the emission spectral change of metal sensor titration curve as shown in Fig. 13. For the ratiometric study, 1.5 μM **1** in HEPES buffer was continuously titrated with increasing concentration of Cd^{2+} ion. The spectra show the generation of blue shifted emission band with maxima $\sim 476 \text{ nm}$. After the completion of the complexation process with Cd^{2+} ion, the resultant solution was titrated with Zn^{2+} ion.

With continuous increase in the Zn^{2+} ion concentration, the concomitant enhancement of the emission band was observed with emission maxima at $\sim 476 \text{ nm}$. The resultant solution was kept for 30 min and then the emission spectrum was recorded. Spectral band position and emission intensity ($\Phi = 0.280$) were found to be intact which suggests that the L- Zn^{2+} complex is more stable than the L- Cd^{2+} complex. The ratiometric displacement is presented in Scheme 1.

Fig. 10. HRMS analysis of the solution **1** + Zn²⁺ and complex **2** (solid state). In both solution state and solid state a peak appeared at 409. This indicates that the probable molecular formula is [Zn₂(L)₂](ClO₄)₂.

Fig. 10a. Probable structure of **3**.

Fig. 11. Effect of the pH on the fluorescence intensity of **1** (40 μM).

Fig. 12. Fluorescence titration of **1** + Zn²⁺ complex with EDTA in a HEPES buffer [50 μM, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 °C (λ_{exc} = 350 nm). Intensity gradually decreases upon gradual addition of EDTA (total 100 μM) solution.

Fig. 13. The ratiometric displacement of Cd²⁺ ion from L-Cd²⁺ complex by Zn²⁺ ion in a HEPES buffer [50 μM, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 °C (λ_{exc} = 350 nm).

Time resolved measurement :

Picosecond time-resolved fluorescence technique has been used to examine the excited state behavior of the free sensor **1** and its metal complexes in MeOH solvent (Fig. 14). According to the equations³¹ $\tau^{-1} = k_r + k_{nr}$ and $k_r = \Phi_f/\tau$, the radiative rate constant k_r and the total nonradiative rate constant k_{nr} of **1** and Zn^{2+} -bound species were calculated.

Fig. 14. Time-resolved fluorescence decay of **1** (green), **1**+ Cd^{2+} (blue), **1**+ Zn^{2+} (red) and prompt (black) ($\lambda_{ex} = 350$ nm).

The fluorescence decay curve for the sensor **1** and its metal complexes were fitted by bi-exponential function with acceptable χ^2 values and all the data are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Fluorescence lifetimes of free chemosensor **1** and its complexes in MeOH solvent

MeOH	τ_1 (ns)	τ_2 (ns)	τ_3 (ns)	a_1	a_2	a_3	χ^2	τ_{av}	ϕ	k_r (s^{-1}) $\times 10^8$	Fold w.r.t.	k_{nr} (s^{-1}) $\times 10^8$
1	3.58	26.21	0.72	0.84	0.13	0.67	1.16	14.39	0.020	0.013	–	0.681
2 (1 + Cd^{2+})	1.91	12.92	0.12	4.68	4.88	0.99	1.144	11.38	0.13	0.114	8	0.764
3 (1 + Zn^{2+})	1.38	12.37	0.17	0.05	1.44	4.14	1.23	0.54	0.280	5.09	366	13.103

The data suggest that the factor that induces fluorescent enhancement is mainly due to the more than 366 times increase of k_r . This enhancement is attributed to the introduction of Zn^{2+} and the strong complexation occurring with **1**, as is evident from the large binding constant value. Upon complexation, the lone pair of electrons on the N atom of the chemosensor **1** is no longer available for PET³⁴, leading to fluorescence enhancement.

DFT and TD DFT calculations :

The geometry of **2** and **3** are fully optimized by DFT/B3LYP method using Gaussian03 software. The optimized structural parameters are summarized in Tables 4 and 5 in the Supporting Information for complexes **2** and **3** respectively. The calculated bond parameters are fairly well reproduced the X-ray crystal structure data for complex **3**.

The optimized geometry of **3** is represented in Fig. 15. The bond distances and bond angles are close to the literature values³⁵. Contour plots of some selected molecular orbitals are given in Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 for **2** and **3** respectively.

The high energy occupied molecular orbitals (HOMOs) and low energy unoccupied molecular orbitals (LUMOs) have been constituted by >90% ligand group of orbitals with a HOMO-LUMO energy gap is 3.58 eV and 3.56 eV for **2** and **3** respectively.

To get detailed insight into the electronic spectra of the complexes, TDDFT/CPCM calculations have been performed in methanol. The calculated singlet-singlet vertical electronic transitions are summarized in Tables 6 and 7 in the Supporting Information for **2** and **3** respectively. The calculated electronic transitions are very close to the experimental electronic bands. All the transitions in the complexes have intra-ligand charge transfer (ILCT) origin.

Cell studies :

The intracellular Zn^{2+} imaging behavior of **1** was stud-

ied on A375, a human melanoma cell line, by fluorescence microscopy. After incubation with chemosensor **1** (20 μ M) at 37 °C for 10 min, the cells displayed very faint intracellular fluorescence (Fig. 18B).

However, cells exhibited intense fluorescence when exogenous Zn^{2+} was introduced into the cell via incubation with a zinc nitrate salt solution (Fig. 18C-E). The intensive fluorescence behavior was, however, strongly

Table-4 (contd.)

Table 4. Correlation between experimental and theoretical bond lengths and bond angles of **2**

Bonds (Å)	X-Ray	DFT
Cd1-O1	2.2440(13)	2.301
Cd1-N1	2.2946(19)	2.367
Cd1-N3	2.339(2)	2.402
Cd2-O1	2.2449(13)	2.302
Cd2-N4	2.301(2)	2.368
Cd2-N6	2.3627(18)	2.403
Angles (°)		
O1-Cd1-N1	141.53(7)	138.6
O1-Cd1-N3	74.75(6)	74.07
O1-Cd1-O1_a	73.94(5)	75.49
O1-Cd1-N1_a	107.57(6)	105.6
O1-Cd1-N3_a	117.86(6)	119.2
N1-Cd1-N3	70.93(6)	69.60
N1-Cd1-N1_a	94.49(7)	95.61
N1-Cd1-N3_a	98.82(6)	97.61
N3-Cd1-N3_a	165.31(6)	163.0
O1-Cd2-N4	103.06(6)	103.6
O1-Cd2-N6	125.23(6)	123.9
O1-Cd2-O1_a	73.90(5)	74.45
O1-Cd2-N4_a	132.74(7)	133.8
O1-Cd2-N6_a	74.04(6)	74.07
N4-Cd2-N6	70.21(6)	69.06
N4-Cd2-N4_a	111.06(7)	109.0
N4-Cd2-N6_a	97.17(7)	97.80
N6-Cd2-N6_a	158.22(6)	159.4
Cd2-N6-N5	113.82(12)	113.2

O1-Zn2-N4	101.9
O1-Zn2-N6	122.7
O1-Zn2-O1_a	74.51
O1-Zn2-N4_a	139.6
O1-Zn2-N6_a	76.42
N4-Zn2-N6	72.27
N4-Zn2-N4_a	105.1
N4-Zn2-N6_a	94.09
N6-Zn2-N6_a	157.9
Zn2-N6-N5	113.3

Fig. 15. Optimized structure of Zn-complex (Blue : N, Pink : Zn, Red : O atoms).**Table 5.** Theoretical bond lengths and bond angles of **3**

Bonds (Å)	Calcd.
Zn1-O1	2.117
Zn1-N1	2.243
Zn1-N3	2.299
Zn2-O1	2.118
Zn2-N4	2.243
Zn2-N6	2.297
Angles (°)	
O1-Zn1-N1	139.6
O1-Zn1-N3	76.42
O1-Zn1-O1_a	74.51
O1-Zn1-N1_a	101.9
O1-Zn1-N3_a	122.6
N1-Zn1-N3	72.27
N1-Zn1-N1_a	101.2
N1-Zn1-N3_a	95.08
N3-Zn1-N3_a	159.9

suppressed when either EDTA or TPEN (100 μ M) was also added to the medium. Because of the fact that both EDTA and TPEN have a strong tendency to bind with Zn²⁺ ion, the sensors with fluorescence property were competitively inhibited to bind with Zn²⁺ ions; hence the intensive fluorescence disappeared (Fig. 18F and 18G). Therefore, this renders a confirmatory evidence of the sensor to have a specific ability to sense Zn²⁺ ions. The fluorescence responses of **1** with various concentrations of added Zn²⁺ are clearly evident from the cellular imaging. Hence, these results indicate that **1** is an efficient candidate for monitoring changes in the intracellular Zn²⁺ concentration under biological conditions and in order to test its cytotoxicity, we performed MTT assay in human melanoma cancer cells treated with various concentra-

Fig. 16. Contour plots of some selected molecular orbitals of Cd-complex.

Fig. 17. Contour plots of some selected molecular orbitals of Zn-complex.

Table 6. Vertical electronic transition calculated by TDDFT/CPCM method for complex **2**

$E_{\text{Excitation}}$ (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{Excitation}}$ (nm)	Osc. strength (<i>f</i>)	Key transitions	Character
2.9695	417.5	0.2009	(55%)HOMO-1→LUMO (42%)HOMO→LUMO+1	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
2.9999	413.3	0.4052	(87%)HOMO→LUMO	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.1579	392.6	0.1055	(87%)HOMO-1→LUMO+1	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.6655	338.2	0.1958	(68%)HOMO-2→LUMO+2	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.7193	333.4	0.4935	(63%)HOMO-2→LUMO+1 (32%)HOMO-3→LUMO	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.9335	315.2	0.1465	(44%)HOMO→LUMO+5 (35%)HOMO-1→LUMO+4	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.9509	313.8	0.1826	(72%)HOMO-1→LUMO+5	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT

Table 7. Vertical electronic transition calculated by TDDFT/CPCM method for complex **3**

$E_{\text{Excitation}}$ (eV)	$\lambda_{\text{Excitation}}$ (nm)	Osc. strength (<i>f</i>)	Key transitions	Character
3.0105	411.9	0.1560	(54%)HOMO-1→LUMO (44%)HOMO→LUMO+1	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.0202	410.5	0.2017	(94%)HOMO→LUMO	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.2101	386.2	0.1320	(93%)HOMO-1→LUMO+1	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.5915	345.2	0.2382	(92%)HOMO-2→LUMO+2	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.7037	334.8	0.5327	(61%)HOMO-2→LUMO+1 (30%)HOMO-3→LUMO	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
3.9088	317.2	0.2042	(78%)HOMO→LUMO+4	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
4.0147	308.8	0.1255	(52%)HOMO→LUMO+5 (39%)HOMO-1→LUMO+4	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT
4.3844	282.8	0.1685	(84%)HOMO-2→LUMO+5	L(π)→L(π^*), ILCT

Fig. 18. (A) Phase contrast image of A375 cells, (B) fluorescence image of A375 cells incubated with 20 μM chemosensor **1** for 10 min at 37°C. Chemosensor **1** (20 μM) incubated cells were washed with PBS and were exposed to increasing concentrations of extracellular Zn²⁺ ion, like (C) 10 μM , (D) 20 μM and (E) 50 μM . Images showing disappearance of fluorescence intensity in the chemosensor **1** and Zn²⁺ ion treated A375 cells after the addition of 100 μM EDTA (F) and 100 μM TPEN (G), respectively. For all imaging, the samples were excited at 350 nm.

Fig. 19. % cell viability of A375 cells treated with different concentrations (1–100 μM) of chemosensor **1** for four hours as determined by MTT assay. Results are expressed as mean \pm S.E. of three independent experiments.

tions of chemosensor **1** for up to 4 h. As shown in Fig. 18A, 20 μM **1** did not show significant cytotoxic effects on human melanoma cancer cells for at least up to 4 h of its treatment. This thus suggests that **1** can be readily used for cellular application at the indicated dose and time of incubation without much concern about its cytotoxicity (Fig. 19).

Conclusions

In conclusion, we have successfully developed a new 2,6-diformyl-4-methylphenol based fluorescent chemical probe **1**, and it displays high selectivity and sensitivity for Zn^{2+} in a HEPES buffer [50 mM, DMSO : water = 1 : 9 (v/v), pH = 7.2] at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. In the presence of Zn^{2+} , significant fluorescence enhancement is achieved, and it is found that the quantum yield was increased more than 14-fold. This is accounted for the formation of the Zn^{2+} complex **3** with a high value of the binding constant. By incubation of cultured living cells (A375) with **1**, intracellular Zn^{2+} concentrations could be monitored through selective fluorescence sensing.

References

1. J. J. R. F. da Silva and R. J. P. Williams, "The Biological Chemistry of the Elements", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1993.
2. B. L. Vallee and K. H. Falchuk, *Physiol. Rev.*, 1993, **73**, 79.
3. D. S. Auld, *BioMetals*, 2001, **14**, 271.
4. S. L. Galasso and R. H. Dyck, *Mol. Med.*, 2007, **13**, 380.
5. A. I. Bush, W. H. Pettingell, G. Multhaup, M. D. Paradis, J. P. Vonsattel, J. F. Gusella, K. Beyreuther, C. L. Masters

- and R. E. Tanzi, *Science*, 1994, **265**, 1464.
6. A. I. Bush, W. H. Pettingell, M. D. Paradis and R. E. Tanzi, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1994, **269**, 12152.
7. L. C. Costello, Y. Liu, J. Zou and R. B. Franklin, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1999, **274**, 17499.
8. S. M. Henshall, D. E. H. Afar, K. K. Rasiah, L. G. Horvath, K. Gish, I. Caras, V. Ramakrishnan, M. Wong, U. Jeffry and J. G. Kench, *Oncogene*, 2003, **22**, 6005.
9. (a) J. R. Lakowicz, "Principles of Fluorescence Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Kluwer Academic/Plenum, New York, 1999; (b) L. Xue, Q. Liu and H. Jiang, *Org. Lett.*, 2009, **11**, 3454.
10. (a) K. Sapsford, E. L. Berti and I. L. Medintz, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 4562; (b) W. H. Chen, Y. Xing and Y. Pang, *Org. Lett.*, 2011, **13**, 1362.
11. (a) M. Lowry, S. O. Fakayode, M. L. Geng, G. A. Baker, L. Wang, M. E. McCarrole, G. Patonay and I. M. Warner, *Anal. Chem.*, 2008, **80**, 4551; (b) Z. Liu, C. Zhang, Y. Li, Z. Wu, F. Qian, X. Yang, W. He, X. Gao and Z. Guo, *Org. Lett.*, 2009, **11**, 795.
12. F. A. Callan, A. P. de Silva and D. C. Magri, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 8551.
13. P. D. Zalewski, I. J. Forbes, R. F. Seamark, R. Borlinghaus, W. H. Betts, S. F. Lincoln and A. D. Ward, *Chem. Biol.*, 1994, **1**, 153.
14. Y. Zhang, X. Guo, W. Si, L. Jia and X. Qian, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 473.
15. X. Zhang, D. Hayes, S. J. Smith, S. Friedle and S. J. Lippard, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 15788.
16. M. Taki, J. L. Wolford and T. V. O'Halloran, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 712.
17. K. Komatsu, Y. Urano, H. Kojima and T. Nagano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 13447.
18. Y. Mikata, M. Wakamatsu, A. Kawamura, N. Yamanaka, S. Yano, A. Odani, K. Morihiro and S. Tamotsu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 9262.

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19. (a) L. Xue, Q. Liu and H. Jiang, *Org. Lett.*, 2009, **11**, 3454; (b) T. Gunnlaugsson, *Tetrahedron*, 2004, **60**, 11239; (c) L. Xue, G. Li, Q. Liu, H. Wang, C. Liu, X. Ding, S. He and H. Jiang, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 3680.
20. R. R. Gagne, C. L. Spiro, T. J. Smith, C. A. Hamann, W. R. Thies and A. K. Shiemeke, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 4073.
21. T. N. Mandal, S. Roy, S. Konar, A. Jana, K. Das, S. Ray, S. Gupta, R. Saha, M. S. El-Fallah, J. Tercero, R. J. Butcher, S. Chatterjee and S. K. Kar, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 413.
22. B. K. Paul and N. Guchhait, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2011, **115**, 11938.
23. B. Bhattacharya, S. Nakka, L. Guruprasad and A. Samanta, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2009, **113**, 2143.
24. A. D. Becke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1993, **98**, 5645; (b) C. Lee, W. Yang and R. G. Parr, *Phys. Rev. (B)*, 1988, **37**, 785.
25. Gaussian 03, Revision D. 01, M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), T. Vreven, K. N. Kudin, J. C. Burant, J. M. Millam, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, M. Cossi, G. Scalmani, N. Rega, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, M. Klene, X. Li, J. E. Knox, H. P. Hratchian, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, P. Y. Ayala, K. Morokuma, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, V. G. Zakrzewski, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, M. C. Strain, O. Farkas, D. K. Malick, A. D. Rabuck, K. Raghavachari, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, Q. Cui, A. G. Baboul, S. Clifford, J. Cioslowski, B. B. Stefanov, G. Liu, A. Liashenko, P. Piskorz, I. Komaromi, R. L. Martin, D. J. Fox, T. Keith, M. A. Al-Laham, C. Y. Peng, A. Nanayakkara, M. Challacombe, P. M. W. Gill, B. Johnson, W. Chen, M. W. Wong, C. Gonzalez and J. A. Pople, Gaussian 03, Gaussian, Inc., Wallingford, CT, 2004.
26. P. J. Hay and W. R. Wadt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 270; (b) W. R. Wadt and P. J. Hay, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 284; (c) P. J. Hay and W. R. Wadt, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1985, **82**, 299.
27. R. Bauernschmitt and R. Ahlrichs, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1996, **256**, 454; (b) R. E. Stratmann, G. E. Scuseria and M. J. Frisch, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **109**, 8218. (c) M. E. Casida, C. Jamorski, K. C. Casida and D. R. Salahub, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **108**, 4439.
28. V. Barone and M. Cossi, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1998, **102**, 1995; (b) M. Cossi and V. Barone, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 2001, **115**, 4708; (c) M. Cossi, N. Rega, G. Scalmani and V. Barone, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2003, **24**, 669.
29. N. M. O'Boyle, A. L. Tenderholt and K. M. Langner, *J. Comput. Chem.*, 2008, **29**, 839.
30. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr., Sect. A*, 2008, **64**, 112.
31. U. C. Saha, B. Chattopadhyay, K. Dhara, S. K. Mandal, S. Sarkar, A. R. Khuda-Bukhsh, M. Mukherjee, M. Helliwell and P. Chattopadhyay, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 1213.
32. B. Valeur, "Molecular Fluorescence : Principles and Applications", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, Germany, 2002.
33. K. Dhara, U. C. Saha, A. Dan, S. Sarkar, M. Manassero and P. Chattopadhyay, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 1754.
34. N. J. Turro, "Modern Molecular Photochemistry", Benjamin Cummings, Menlo Park, CA, 1978.
35. A. Guha, T. Chattopadhyay, N. D. Paul, M. Mukherjee, S. Goswami, T. K. Mondal, E. Zangrando and D. Das, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 8750.

